

D2.1 Application Ontologies

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Executive Summary

This report outlines the work conducted to establish standardized data models and ontologies for generating linked battery data in line with the FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) principles in the DigiBatt project. The aim is to ensure that battery test data can be mapped to relevant domain ontologies and integrated into commonly used programming languages.

The task involved the creation of module and application ontologies to describe battery testing workflows, equipment, and models. These ontologies, designed as extensions of the Elementary Multiperspective Materials Ontology (EMMO) battery domain ensure interoperability with other research activities within the DigiBatt project and the wider battery research community. In addition, specific safety-testing ontologies were developed to define key parameters for lithium-ion battery safety testing at both the cell and stack levels. These parameters, identified through collaborative efforts, are critical for safety and lifetime simulations and can be used in predictive models.

The development of these ontologies enables automated extraction of relevant parameters from test data, minimizing manual intervention, and provides a standardized framework for future battery testing and research. The deliverable represents a significant step toward improving data consistency and interoperability across the battery research ecosystem, supporting advanced data analytics and AI-driven predictions.

Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
CC-CV	Constant Current Constant Voltage
EMMO	Elementary Multiperspective Materials Ontology
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FOOPS	FAIR Ontology Pitfall Scanner
PyBaMM	Python Battery Mathematical Modelling
RDF	Resource Description Framework
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium

1. Introduction

This report documents the work conducted within the DigiBatt project under Task 2.1 Create Application Ontologies and Standard Data Models, resulting in deliverable D2.1: Application Ontologies. The focus of this task was to develop application ontologies that provide a standardized framework for generating linked battery data in line with FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability)[1], [2]. These ontologies facilitate the mapping of battery test data to relevant domain ontologies, ensuring compatibility with common programming languages.

The deliverable is not this report itself but rather the ontologies developed and published as part of the domain-battery ontology, which can be accessed at <https://github.com/emmo-repo/domain-battery>. These ontologies are designed to enable the creation of linked data descriptions for battery testing processes, as well as the resulting data. This structured approach ensures the traceability and interoperability of data throughout the entire lifecycle of battery testing.

By using these ontologies, researchers can document and link all aspects of battery testing—from the test equipment and processes to the resulting data. Crucially, this data can be coupled with detailed descriptions of the battery cells and materials being tested, ensuring traceability from the material level to the final test outcomes. This level of detail is essential for maintaining accurate, reusable data that can be integrated across platforms and research efforts.

The application ontologies developed here are extensions of the EMMO domain-battery ontology and describe the workflows, equipment, and models used in battery testing. In addition, safety-focused ontologies were created to identify critical parameters in lithium-ion battery testing at the cell level. These parameters support AI-driven predictions for safety and lifetime simulations, ensuring that the data generated can be used for advanced analytics and decision-making.

The following sections of this report will outline the methodology used to develop these ontologies, the resulting data models, and their importance in advancing the management and utilization of battery test data.

2. Methodology

The application ontologies developed for this deliverable were created using a structured methodology rooted in best practices for ontology engineering and linked data. Central to this effort is the EMMO¹ framework, which provides a robust foundation for representing scientific and engineering knowledge. Developing these ontologies within

¹ <https://github.com/emmo-repo/EMMO>

the EMMO framework ensures alignment with broader efforts to formalize knowledge in materials science and related domains.

These ontologies are designed as extensions of the domain-battery ontology, a key component within the EMMO suite. This ensures compatibility with existing battery-related ontologies while allowing for specialized descriptions of battery testing processes and data. Building on the domain-battery ontology maintains coherence across different areas of battery research, testing, and manufacturing. Additionally, the ontologies adhere to best practice recommendations by adopting a modular design. This approach not only facilitates re-use of the developed ontologies but also supports their future extension and integration with other ontologies, ensuring that the knowledge captured can evolve and be reused in new contexts.

The ontologies are also built on the EMMO domain-characterisation-methodology ontology, which provides a framework for representing scientific methods and characterization techniques. This allowed us to incorporate detailed descriptions of battery testing workflows, equipment, and outputs in a way that aligns with existing methodologies for experimental data representation.

The terms and concepts in the ontologies were defined following established standards and recommendations in the field of battery research and electrochemistry, supplemented with input from domain experts. By blending these formal standards with practical insights, we ensured that the ontologies capture both the theoretical and applied dimensions of battery testing and can support real-world use cases.

Following best practices outlined by the W3C (World Wide Web Consortium), the ontologies are written in the Turtle format², a standard for Resource Description Framework (RDF)³. Turtle ensures that the ontologies are machine-readable, sharable, and compatible with various semantic web tools. This adherence to established best practices ensures interoperability and long-term sustainability of the data models.

Additionally, the ontologies are designed to comply with FOOPS recommendations (FAIR Ontology Pitfall Scanner)⁴ which provide guidance for ontology development in industrial and engineering contexts. Following these guidelines ensures the ontologies meet high standards of formal development while being practically applicable for battery research.

A key principle guiding the development of these ontologies is the re-use of existing ontologies wherever possible. By building on well-established ontologies like EMMO and domain-characterisation-methodology⁵, we ensure that the ontologies remain interoperable with other ontology frameworks and datasets. This strategy not only

² <https://www.w3.org/TR/turtle/>

³ <https://www.w3.org/RDF/>

⁴ https://foops.linkeddata.es/FAIR_validator.html

⁵ <https://github.com/emmo-repo/domain-characterisation-methodology>

reduces redundancy but also fosters a more integrated and cohesive ecosystem of knowledge representation in the battery research domain.

The ontologies are further supported by practical examples in JSON-LD, a user-friendly and machine-readable format. These examples demonstrate how the ontologies can be used to create linked data descriptions of battery testing processes and results. They also illustrate how these descriptions can be integrated with battery cell and material data, enabling full traceability throughout the lifecycle of battery testing and development. This modular, re-usable structure ensures that the ontologies can easily evolve and be extended to new applications as the needs of the research community grow.

The methodology ensures that the ontologies developed under this task are not only interoperable and practical but also built to foster long-term re-use and scalability in the field of battery testing. By adhering to modular design principles, re-using existing ontologies, and following best practices for RDF and semantic web development, these ontologies are well-positioned to support ongoing advancements in battery research.

3. Ontologies

The ontologies developed in this deliverable were designed to address two key areas essential for battery research and testing: the representation of testing workflows and the detailed description of battery cell geometries. These ontologies form a modular extension of the domain-battery ontology, ensuring interoperability and reuse across various testing scenarios and research efforts. Below, we provide an overview of the two main ontologies created to support these needs.

3.1 Battery Testing Ontology

The battery-testing.ttl ontology was developed to support the creation of semantic, linked data descriptions of battery testing processes and their results. Its primary objective is to improve reproducibility, interoperability, and automation of battery testing workflows by providing a standardized framework for describing tests, tasks, measurements, and equipment in a machine-readable format. By doing so, the ontology allows battery test data to be linked, shared, and reused across research platforms and systems in a consistent and traceable manner.

The ontology is focused on defining key terms and concepts related to battery testing, with particular emphasis on:

- **Test Methods:** Standardized terms for a wide variety of performance and safety test methods, such as cycling, Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS), Galvanostatic Intermittent Titration Technique (GITT), and thermal runaway tests. These methods form the foundation of the testing process, each with specific inputs, outputs, and procedures.

- **Test Workflows and Tasks:** Descriptions of the various tasks and subprocesses involved in testing workflows, including charging, discharging, resting, heating, and cooling. These terms allow researchers to specify the sequence of actions in a test and how each task is related to the overall procedure.
- **Semiotic Measurements:** The ontology includes terms for key measurements collected during testing, such as voltage, current, and temperature. These measurements are treated as integral outputs of the testing process, enabling detailed tracking of test results and battery performance.
- **Testing Equipment:** Definitions for various types of equipment used during testing, such as potentiostats, battery cyclers, and climate chambers. This ensures that the tools and devices involved in a test can be linked directly to the processes they are used in, providing traceability and transparency in testing protocols.
- **Test Data:** Descriptions of the table schemas used to represent the structured data collected from tests. This includes how the data is organized, stored, and linked to the test processes, measurements, and equipment.

Within the EMMO framework, each test is described as a Process, linked to its inputs (e.g., battery cells, components), outputs (e.g., test results, measurements), parameters (e.g., environmental conditions), equipment, and specific tasks or subprocesses (e.g., charging, resting). This approach ensures that the testing process is not only described in a high-level abstract manner but also broken down into granular, actionable steps that can be linked and traced across different experiments and systems.

The battery-testing.ttl ontology is modular and extendable, allowing it to evolve as new testing methods, equipment, and workflows are introduced in the field of battery research. This flexibility ensures that researchers can easily integrate new types of tests and measurements into their linked data descriptions, supporting the growing needs of the battery research community.

3.2 Battery Cell Geometry Ontology

The battery-cell-geometry.ttl ontology was developed to address the need for precise descriptions of the physical dimensions and structure of battery cells, including their form factors, surface areas, and lengths. This ontology plays a critical role in representing various cell types, such as pouch, cylindrical, and prismatic cells, and provides detailed descriptions of faces and edges relevant to each cell type.

The battery cell geometry ontology was developed to meet the need to define specific locations for placing sensors during testing. In tests like thermal runaway or temperature profiling, the placement of sensors can be critical to capturing accurate data on the cell's performance and behavior under stress. The battery cell geometry ontology allows users to describe these sensor placements in a standardized way, linking them to specific faces,

surfaces, or points on the cell. This level of detail ensures that testing procedures are both reproducible and traceable across different studies and testing environments.

By providing a structured and flexible way to describe battery geometries, the battery cell geometry ontology enables seamless integration with the battery testing ontology, supporting a holistic approach to describing the design, testing, and analysis of battery cells.

In the following sub-sections, different types of battery geometries that are included in the battery cell geometry ontology are described. The origin of the coordinate system is placed at the centre of volume of the bounding surfaces, excluding the current terminals. Unless otherwise stated, cell orientation is such that the largest surface is facing towards the ground with the positive terminal on the left side. In the case of cylindrical cells, the cell is positioned with the positive terminal facing upwards.

The cell geometry is described as a collection of surfaces and lengths. Lengths in the y-direction are designated with the variable a , z-direction b , and x-direction c . Surfaces are denoted with upper-case letters, describing the faces bound by different lengths. For example, the face bounded by length b and c is denoted BC . The surface bounded by lengths b_2 and c_3 is $B2C3$

Paired Terminal Prismatic Cell with Top-Facing Vent

Figure 1. Overview of the cell geometry surface and length definitions for a paired terminal prismatic cell with a top-facing vent

3.2.1 Paired Terminal Prismatic cell with Bottom-Facing Vent

Figure 2. Overview of the cell geometry surface and length definitions for a paired terminal prismatic cell with a bottom-facing vent

3.2.2 Opposite Terminal Prismatic Cell with Bottom-Facing Vent

Figure 3. Overview of the cell geometry surface and length definitions for a opposite terminal prismatic cell with a bottom-facing vent

3.2.3 Opposite Terminal Prismatic Cell with Side-Facing Vent

Figure 4. Overview of the cell geometry surface and length definitions for a opposite terminal prismatic cell with a side-facing vent

3.2.4 Opposite Terminal Pouch Cell with Sealing Seam

Figure 5. Overview of the cell geometry surface and length definitions for a opposite terminal pouch cell with a sealing seam

3.2.5 Opposite Terminal Pouch Cell without Sealing Seam

Figure 6. Overview of the cell geometry surface and length definitions for an opposite terminal pouch cell without a sealing seam

3.2.6 Paired Terminal Pouch Cell with Sealing Seam

Figure 7. Overview of the cell geometry surface and length definitions for a paired terminal pouch cell with a sealing seam

3.2.7 Opposite Terminal Cylindrical Cell

Figure 8. Overview of the cell geometry surface and length definitions for an opposite terminal cylindrical cell

3.2.8 Paired Terminal Cylindrical Cell

Figure 9. Overview of the cell geometry surface and length definitions for a paired terminal cylindrical cell

4. Data Models

Data models were developed to operationalize the concepts defined in the ontologies and to support the creation of linked data descriptions for battery testing. These data models leverage the structure provided by the battery-testing.ttl and battery-cell-

geometry.ttl ontologies to ensure that test data can be accurately and consistently represented.

The data models provide a framework for:

- Describing battery cells in terms of their physical dimensions, using the battery cell geometry ontology.
- Capturing the full lifecycle of a test, from the input battery cell, through the test process, to the results and equipment used, using the battery testing ontology.
- Linking test data back to specific battery cell geometries, ensuring that test results are traceable to the exact physical configuration of the cell during testing.

In addition to these developments, the data models are being implemented as part of a Python package designed for working with battery test data. This package will be published as part of the upcoming DigiBatt Deliverable D3.1 and will provide tools for automating the creation and management of linked data for battery testing. The package will integrate with the developed ontologies, offering a flexible and scalable solution for handling test data in compliance with the FAIR principles, promoting interoperability, traceability, and data reuse across platforms.

4.1 Examples

4.1.1 Test Procedure Descriptions

Writing machine-readable testing procedures is one basic aspect of battery testing that is supported by the battery testing ontology. In this example, we want to describe a CC-CV cycling test procedure, in which the cell first rests for 1 hour, then is charged at 1C to a voltage of 4.2 V, held at 4.2 V until the current is less than or equal to 0.01C, then discharged at 1C to a voltage limit of 3 V. The cycling loop is repeated 10 times, and finally a 1 hour resting period is again defined.

Expressed as a PyBaMM experimental procedure, the test is:

```
Rest for 1 h
(Charging at 1 C until 4.2 V -> Hold at 4.2 V until 0.01 C -> Discharging at 1 C until
3 V) * 10
Rest for 1 h'
```

When combined with the relevant testing metadata and expressed as a JSON-LD object, the test description is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Example test procedure description for a CC-CV cycling test in JSON-LD

```
{
  "@context": "https://w3id.org/emmo/domain/electrochemistry/context",
```

```

"@type": [
  "ConstantCurrentConstantVoltageCycling",
  "IterativeWorkflow"
],
"rdfs:label": "GeneratedBatteryTestProcedure",
"rdfs:comment": "A description of a generated battery testing
procedure",
"hasOperator": {
  "@type": "schema:Person",
  "@id": "https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8758-6109",
  "rdfs:label": "Simon Clark"
},
"hasLab": {
  "@type": "Laboratory",
  "@id": "https://ror.org/01f677e56",
  "rdfs:label": "SINTEF"
},
"hasCharacterisationEnvironment": {
  "@type": "CharacterisationEnvironment",
  "rdfs:label": "SINTEF Battery Lab",
  "rdfs:comment": "Ambient conditions in the SINTEF Battery Lab",
  "hasCharacterisationEnvironmentProperty": [
    {
      "@type": "AmbientCelsiusTemperature",
      "hasNumericalPart": {
        "@type": "Real",
        "hasNumericalValue": 25
      },
      "hasMeasurementUnit": "emmo:DegreeCelsius"
    }
  ]
},
"hasTask": {
  "@type": "Resting",
  "hasInput": [
    {
      "@type": "Duration",
      "hasNumericalPart": {
        "@type": "Real",
        "hasNumericalValue": 1
      },
      "hasMeasurementUnit": "emmo:Hour"
    }
  ]
},
"hasNext": {
  "@type": "IterativeWorkflow",
  "hasInput": [
    {

```

```

    "@type": "NumberOfIterations",
    "hasNumericalPart": {
      "@type": "Real",
      "hasNumericalValue": 10
    },
    "hasMeasurementUnit": "emmo:UnitOne"
  }
],
"hasTask": {
  "@type": "Charging",
  "hasInput": [
    {
      "@type": "Current",
      "hasNumericalPart": {
        "@type": "Real",
        "hasNumericalValue": 1
      },
      "hasMeasurementUnit": "emmo:AmperePerAmpereHour"
    },
    {
      "@type": [
        "VoltageLimitLimit",
        "TerminationCondition"
      ],
      "hasNumericalPart": {
        "@type": "Real",
        "hasNumericalValue": 4.2
      },
      "hasMeasurementUnit": "emmo:Volt"
    }
  ],
"hasNext": {
  "@type": "Hold",
  "hasInput": [
    {
      "@type": "Voltage",
      "hasNumericalPart": {
        "@type": "Real",
        "hasNumericalValue": 4.2
      },
      "hasMeasurementUnit": "emmo:Volt"
    },
    {
      "@type": [
        "CurrentLimitLimit",
        "TerminationCondition"
      ],
      "hasNumericalPart": {

```


4.1.2 Test Data Table Schemas

For machines to process the results of a battery test, they often require a schema to interpret the meaning of the columns in tabular data. The RDF vocabulary CSVW provides a general framework for expressing table schemas. The example below shows how this can be applied and combined with terms from the ontology to create a table schema for cycler data from a specific manufacturer.

```
{
  "@context": "https://w3id.org/emmo/domain/battery/context",
  "@type": "csvw:TableSchema",
  "@id": "https://w3id.org/emmo/application/cycler-data#",
  "dc:identifier": "https://doi.org/10.1234/example.doi",
  "dc:title": "Biologic Cycler Data Table Schema",
  "dc:description": "A table schema describing csv files exported from
battery cycler equipment manufactured by Biologic",
  "dc:subject": ["battery", "data", "biologic", "cycler", "cycling"],
  "dc:language": "en",
  "dc:license": {
    "@id": "https://spdx.org/licenses/MIT.html"
  },
  "dc:accessRights": "public",
  "dc:publisher": {
    "@type": "schema:ResearchOrganization",
    "@id": "https://ror.org/01f677e56",
    "schema:name": "SINTEF AS"
  },
  "dc:creator": {
    "@type": "schema:Person",
    "@id": "https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8758-6109",
    "schema:name": "Simon Clark",
    "schema:affiliation": {
      "@type": "schema:ResearchOrganization",
      "@id": "https://ror.org/01f677e56",
      "schema:name": "SINTEF"
    }
  },
  "dc:modified": {
    "@value": "2024-07-03",
    "@type": "xsd:date"
  },
  "dc:created": {
    "@value": "2024-07-03",
    "@type": "xsd:date"
  }
}
```

```

    },
    "dc:hasVersion": "1.0.0",
    "dc:format": "application/ld+json",
    "schema:name": "Biologic Cycler Data Table Schema",
    "schema:description": "A table schema describing csv files exported from
battery cycler equipment manufactured by Biologic",
    "schema:version": "1.0.0",
    "schema:contactPoint": {
      "@type": "schema:ContactPoint",
      "schema:contactType": "creator",
      "schema:email": "mailto:simon.clark@sintef.no"
    },
    "schema:encodingFormat": "application/ld+json",
    "csvw:columns": [
      {
        "@type": "csvw:Column",
        "csvw:name": "cycle number",
        "csvw:titles": "Cycle Index",
        "dc:description": "the current cycle number in the test",
        "csvw:propertyUrl": {
          "@type": "CycleNumber"
        },
        "hasMeasurementUnit": [
          {
            "@id": "emmo:UnitOne"
          },
          {
            "@id": "unit:UNITLESS"
          }
        ],
        "schema:unitCode": [
          {
            "@id": "emmo:UnitOne"
          },
          {
            "@id": "unit:UNITLESS"
          }
        ],
        "csvw:datatype": "xsd:integer",
        "csvw:required": "false"
      },
      {
        "@type": "csvw:Column",
        "csvw:name": "half cycle",
        "csvw:titles": "Half Cycle",
        "dc:description": "unknown",
        "csvw:datatype": "xsd:integer",
        "csvw:required": "false"
      }
    ]
  }
}

```

```

    },
    {
      "@type": "csvw:Column",
      "csvw:name": "Ecell/V",
      "csvw:titles": "Voltage",
      "csvw:propertyUrl": {
        "@type": "CellVoltage"
      },
      "hasMeasurementUnit": [
        {
          "@id": "emmo:Volt"
        },
        {
          "@id": "unit:V"
        }
      ],
      "schema:unitCode": [
        {
          "@id": "emmo:Volt"
        },
        {
          "@id": "unit:V"
        }
      ],
      "csvw:datatype": "xsd:decimal",
      "csvw:required": "true"
    },
    {
      "@type": "csvw:Column",
      "csvw:name": "I/mA",
      "csvw:titles": "Current",
      "csvw:propertyUrl": {
        "@type": "CellCurrent"
      },
      "hasMeasurementUnit": [
        {
          "@id": "emmo:MilliAmpere"
        },
        {
          "@id": "unit:MilliA"
        }
      ],
      "schema:unitCode": [
        {
          "@id": "emmo:MilliAmpere"
        },
        {
          "@id": "unit:MilliA"
        }
      ]
    }
  ]
}

```

```

    }
  ],
  "csvw:datatype": "xsd:decimal",
  "csvw:required": "true"
},
{
  "@type": "csvw:Column",
  "csvw:name": "Q discharge/mA.h",
  "csvw:titles": "Discharging Capacity",
  "dc:description": "the capacity that has passed through the cell
during discharging",
  "csvw:propertyUrl": {
    "@type": "DischargingCapacity"
  },
  "hasMeasurementUnit": [
    {
      "@id": "emmo:MilliAmpereHour"
    },
    {
      "@id": "unit:MilliA-HR"
    }
  ],
  "schema:unitCode": [
    {
      "@id": "emmo:MilliAmpereHour"
    },
    {
      "@id": "unit:MilliA-HR"
    }
  ],
  "csvw:datatype": "xsd:decimal",
  "csvw:required": "false"
},
{
  "@type": "csvw:Column",
  "csvw:name": "Q charge/mA.h",
  "csvw:titles": "Charging Capacity",
  "dc:description": "the capacity that has passed through the cell
during charging",
  "csvw:propertyUrl": {
    "@type": "ChargingCapacity"
  },
  "hasMeasurementUnit": [
    {
      "@id": "emmo:MilliAmpereHour"
    },
    {
      "@id": "unit:MilliA-HR"
    }
  ],

```

```

    }
  ],
  "schema:unitCode": [
    {
      "@id": "emmo:MilliAmpereHour"
    },
    {
      "@id": "unit:MilliA-HR"
    }
  ],
  "csvw:datatype": "xsd:decimal",
  "csvw:required": "false"
},
{
  "@type": "csvw:Column",
  "csvw:name": "Energy charge/W.h",
  "csvw:titles": "Charging Energy",
  "csvw:propertyUrl": {
    "@type": "ChargingEnergy"
  },
  "hasMeasurementUnit": [
    {
      "@id": "emmo:WattHour"
    },
    {
      "@id": "unit:W-HR"
    }
  ],
  "schema:unitCode": [
    {
      "@id": "emmo:WattHour"
    },
    {
      "@id": "unit:W-HR"
    }
  ],
  "csvw:datatype": "xsd:decimal",
  "csvw:required": "false"
},
{
  "@type": "csvw:Column",
  "csvw:name": "Energy discharge/W.h",
  "csvw:titles": "Discharging Energy",
  "csvw:propertyUrl": {
    "@type": "DischargingEnergy"
  },
  "hasMeasurementUnit": [
    {

```

```

        "@id": "emmo:WattHour"
      },
      {
        "@id": "unit:W-HR"
      }
    ],
    "schema:unitCode": [
      {
        "@id": "emmo:WattHour"
      },
      {
        "@id": "unit:W-HR"
      }
    ],
    "csvw:datatype": "xsd:decimal",
    "csvw:required": "false"
  }
]
}

```

4.1.3 Safety Test Descriptions

Destructive battery testing can also be used to characterise battery safety. In this example, we show how the ontology can be applied to describe a thermal runaway test. In the test below, a battery cell is subjected to external heating until the temperature reaches 200 degrees Celsius, at which point the cell is in thermal runaway. The external heating is turned off and the cell is allowed to cool back to room temperature.

```

{
  "@context": "https://w3id.org/emmo/domain/battery/context",
  "@graph": [
    {
      "@type": "ThermalRunawayTest",
      "rdfs:label": "ThermalRunawayTestProcedure",
      "rdfs:comment": "A description of a thermal runaway test",
      "hasOperator": {
        "@type": "schema:Person",
        "@id": "https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8758-6109",
        "rdfs:label": "Simon Clark"
      },
      "hasLab": {
        "@type": "Laboratory",
        "@id": "https://ror.org/01f677e56",
        "rdfs:label": "SINTEF"
      },
    },
  ],
}

```

```

"hasCharacterisationEnvironment": {
  "@type": "CharacterisationEnvironment",
  "rdfs:label": "SINTEF Battery Lab",
  "rdfs:comment": "Ambient conditions in the SINTEF Battery Lab",
  "hasCharacterisationEnvironmentProperty": [
    {
      "@type": "AmbientCelsiusTemperature",
      "hasNumericalPart": {
        "@type": "Real",
        "hasNumericalValue": 25
      },
      "hasMeasurementUnit": "emmo:DegreeCelsius"
    }
  ]
},
"hasInput": [
  {
    "@type": "BatteryCell",
    "@id": "#battery_cell",
    "hasFormFactor": {
      "@type": "PairedTerminalPrismatic",
      "hasSurface": {
        "@type": "SurfaceCA",
        "@id": "#SurfaceCA"
      }
    }
  }
],
"hasOutput": [
  {
    "@type": "DestroyedBatteryCell"
  },
  {
    "@type": "TestResult",
    "@id": "#test_result",
    "csw:url": "file_path"
  }
],
"hasSubprocess": [
  {
    "@type": "TemperatureMeasurement",
    "hasSample": {
      "@id": "#battery_cell"
    },
    "hasMeasurementDevice": {
      "@type": "Thermocouple",
      "contacts": {
        "@id": "#SurfaceCA"
      }
    }
  }
]

```

```

    },
    "hasProperty": [
      {
        "@type": "PositionVector",
        "hasPart": [
          {
            "@type": "XCoordinate",
            "hasNumericalPart": {
              "@type": "Real",
              "hasNumericalValue": 1
            },
            "hasMeasurementUnit":
"emmo:MilliMetre"
          },
          {
            "@type": "YCoordinate",
            "hasNumericalPart": {
              "@type": "Real",
              "hasNumericalValue": 10
            },
            "hasMeasurementUnit":
"emmo:MilliMetre"
          }
        ]
      }
    ]
  },
  "hasMeasurementParameter": [
    {
      "@type": "MeasurementFrequency",
      "hasNumericalPart": {
        "@type": "Real",
        "hasNumericalValue": 1
      },
      "hasMeasurementUnit": "emmo:Hertz"
    }
  ],
  "hasOutput": {
    "@type": "TemperatureMeasurementResult",
    "@inverse": {
      "hasPart": {
        "@id": "#test_result"
      }
    }
  }
}

```

```

    },
    {
      "@type": "VoltageMeasurement",
      "hasSample": {
        "@id": "#battery_cell"
      },
      "hasMeasurementDevice": {
        "@type": "Voltammeter"
      },
      "hasMeasurementParameter": [
        {
          "@type": "MeasurementFrequency",
          "hasNumericalPart": {
            "@type": "Real",
            "hasNumericalValue": 1
          },
          "hasMeasurementUnit": "emmo:Hertz"
        }
      ],
      "hasOutput": {
        "@type": "VoltageMeasurementResult",
        "@inverse": {
          "hasPart": {
            "@id": "#test_result"
          }
        }
      }
    }
  ],
  {
    "@type": "GasSampling",
    "hasSample": {
      "@id": "#battery_cell"
    },
    "hasMeasurementDevice": {
      "@type": "GasChromatagraph"
    },
    "hasMeasurementParameter": [
      {
        "@type": "MeasurementFrequency",
        "hasNumericalPart": {
          "@type": "Real",
          "hasNumericalValue": 1
        },
        "hasMeasurementUnit": "emmo:Hertz"
      }
    ],
    "hasOutput": {
      "@type": "MeasurementResult",

```

```

        "@inverse": {
            "hasPart": {
                "@id": "#test_result"
            }
        }
    },
    ],
    "hasEquipment": [
        {
            "@type": "ClimateChamber"
        },
        {
            "@type": "BatteryCellHolder"
        }
    ],
    "hasTask": [
        {
            "@type": "ExternalHeating",
            "hasInput": [
                {
                    "@type": "Power",
                    "hasNumericalPart": {
                        "@type": "Real",
                        "hasNumericalValue": 1000
                    },
                    "hasMeasurementUnit": "emmo:Watt"
                },
                {
                    "@type": "TemperatureLimit",
                    "hasNumericalPart": {
                        "@type": "Real",
                        "hasNumericalValue": 200
                    },
                    "hasMeasurementUnit": "emmo:DegreeCelsius"
                }
            ],
        },
        "hasNext": {
            "@type": "ExternalHeating ",
            "hasInput": [
                {
                    "@type": "Power",
                    "hasNumericalPart": {
                        "@type": "Real",
                        "hasNumericalValue": 0
                    },
                    "hasMeasurementUnit": "emmo:Watt"
                }
            ],
        },
    ],

```

```
{
  "@type": "TemperatureLimit",
  "hasNumericalPart": {
    "@type": "Real",
    "hasNumericalValue": 25
  },
  "hasMeasurementUnit": "emmo:DegreeCelsius"
}
]
```

5. Conclusions

The work outlined in this report has focused on the development of application ontologies designed to enable the generation of linked battery test data in compliance with the FAIR principles. By creating modular extensions to the domain-battery ontology, including the `battery-testing.ttl` and `battery-cell-geometry.ttl` modules, a standardized framework has been established to support semantic descriptions of battery testing workflows, equipment, and data. This framework not only enhances the traceability and interoperability of battery test data but also lays the groundwork for future automation in battery research.

The battery-testing ontology provides a comprehensive structure for describing a wide range of test methods, workflows, semiotic measurements, and testing equipment, ensuring that battery tests and their results are fully represented in machine-readable formats. The battery-cell-geometry ontology complements this by offering detailed descriptions of battery cell geometries, which are essential for accurately capturing test setups and sensor placements during testing.

In addition to the ontologies, the development of data models using these ontologies enables the consistent representation of battery test results and their integration into widely-used programming languages. Furthermore, these models are being implemented as part of a Python package to streamline working with battery test data, which will be delivered as part of the Digital Twin framework under Deliverable D3.1.

These developments contribute significantly to improving the reproducibility of battery tests and enhancing collaboration within the research community by providing interoperable, reusable data. As the ontologies and data models are modular and extendable, they are well-suited to accommodate future advancements in battery technology and testing methodologies. Overall, this deliverable establishes a robust foundation for managing and sharing battery test data, ensuring that it can be effectively used across a variety of research platforms and applications.

Ontologies are by nature under continuous development and improvement. This report serves as documentation at the time of writing. For the latest version and guidance, please refer to the source repository, <https://github.com/emmo-repo/domain-battery>

6. References

- [1] S. Clark *et al.*, "Toward a Unified Description of Battery Data," *Adv Energy Mater*, vol. 2102702, 2021, doi: 10.1002/aenm.202102702.
- [2] M. D. Wilkinson *et al.*, "The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship," *Sci Data*, vol. 3, pp. 1–9, 2016, doi: 10.1038/sdata.2016.18.

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